

POTENTIALS OF UTILIZING DEGRADED PLANTAIN PEELS AS A LOCAL BEVERAGE

¹Ajayeoba T.A., ^{1*}Kaka M.O., ²Adeosun I.J., ²Ogenma U.T., ¹Oni M. O., and ²Ekwonwa E.C.

¹Department of Microbiology, Laboratory of Molecular Biology, Immunology and Bioinformatics, Adeleke University, P.M.B 250, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria.

²Division of Microbiology, Department of Biochemistry, Genetics and Microbiology, University of Pretoria, Private Bag X20, Hatfield Pretoria 0028, South Africa.
Department of Public Health, Adeleke University, Ede.

*Corresponding Author Email: kaka.oluwatosin@adelekeuniversity.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Wastes and their disposal have become an environmental concern worldwide especially when these wastes are biodegradable to useful goods and services. Plantain peels, are by-products of the plantain processing which are normally dumped in landfills, rivers or unregulated grounds which constitute environmental pollution. Plantain flour was prepared from non- degraded plantain peels and it was discovered during this research work that plantain flour has high moisture content, lower crude protein, but no crude fiber, no caffeine and it has high Vitamin C with little cyanide. There were observable changes recorded in the nutritional qualities and phytochemical components of the plantain peel samples- the crude fiber protein and moisture contents of the fermented samples had lower values as compared to the unfermented ones. This research work has described the potentials, nutritional and phytochemical components of non-degraded plantain peels as a local beverage low in sugar content which is suitable for a patient suffering from diabetes.

Keywords: Plantain peel, Degradation, Beverage, Waste, Food Safety

INTRODUCTION

Musa paradisiaca is an important staple crop, supplying up to 25% of the carbohydrates for approximately 70 million people in the humid zone of sub-Saharan Africa (IITA, 1998). In some African countries, particularly Nigeria, plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) serves as a major food crop that is usually consumed in the unripe, ripe and over ripe stages. Plantain peels (PL), which constitute 30% of the fruit, are by-products of the plantain processing which are normally dumped in landfills, rivers or unregulated grounds which constitute environmental pollution (Noble *et al.*, 2018). There are various reports on the possible exploration of PL. This waste has been used as an alternative source of dietary fiber and antioxidant Agama-Acevedo *et al.* (2016); Shodehinde and Oboh (2013) to enhance nutritional value of cookies Arun *et al.* (2015), high starch extraction yield Hernández-Carmona *et al.* (2017) and formulation of animal feeds (Okareh *et al.*, 2015). PL contains large quantities of nitrogen, phosphorus and vitamins,

however, its high moisture makes it susceptible to modification by microorganisms. (Arun *et al.*, 2015, Shodehinde and Oboh, 2013).

Wastes and their disposal have become an environmental concern worldwide especially when these wastes are biodegradable to useful goods and services (Shide *et al.*, 2004). However, these wastes can be degraded by the action of some microorganisms and converted to a renewable energy source such as ethanol (Ogunyemi *et al.*, 2015). A variety of microorganisms such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Providencia alcalifaciens*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Aspergillus niger* have been associated in the degradation of plantain derived-wastes (Ogunyemi *et al.*, 2015). The use of fungi in degradation of plantain peels has been reported to have potential of increasing productivity, efficiency and quality output with potential of reducing the cholesterol level (Lawal *et al.*, 2011). Since the fungal degradation have the tendencies of increasing nutritional value of the food waste Lawal *et al.* (2011) and plantain peels have antioxidant properties, there is need to evaluate the potentials of microorganism involved in the degradation and evaluate the fermentation ability in the formulation of plantain peel drink and the nutritional properties. Hence, the aim of this study was to evaluate the potentials of identifying microorganisms involved in the degradation and the use of a promising microorganism in the formulation of fermented drink. Therefore, this study seeks to evaluate the potentials of the microorganisms involved in the degradation and the use of a promising microorganism in the formulation of fermented drink was evaluated.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sample Collection

Plantain samples were obtained from the kitchenette at Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State. All media and reagents used procured from Oxoid and Sigma-Aldrich.

Isolation of Fungi

Fresh matured and ripe plantain peels were chopped into small sizes and divided into two batches. The first batch of 500g was left in an open space for two weeks to dry normally while the second batch of 500g was dried at 50 °C for 48 h in a Gallenkamp oven (Cat. No.IPL 225.WT.1.0) according to Agama-Acevedo *et al.* (2016) until a moisture content of 12% was achieved. Isolation and identification of fungi were carried out on Potatoe Dextrose Agar (PDA) according to the modified method after the drying period (Postmaster *et al.*, 1997). The fungal isolates were sub-cultured until a pure culture was obtained and stored at 80°C for further analysis.

Screening of Aflatoxigenic-Producing Ability

Fungal isolates ten (10) obtained from the two batches of Plantain Peels (degraded and un-degraded) were analyzed for aflatoxigenic producing ability according to the method described by (Gupta and Gopal, 2002). Five (5) Isolates positive for ammonia hydroxide vapour- induced colour change were screened for their aflatoxin production by use of thin layer chromatography according to the method described by (Onilude *et al.*, 2005). The chloroform extracts from the isolates, alongside the standard aflatoxin B1 (Fermentek, Israel) spots showed as blue fluorescence and turned to yellow after spraying with 50% (v/v) sulphuric acid) and viewed under the longwave (365nm) of the ultraviolet light.

Preparation of Plantain Peel Flour

The dried batches of Plantain Peel were pulverized with a warren blender and sieved. Each Plantain Peel powder was stored in a sealed polypropylene plastic bag at room temperature (25 ±2 °C) prior further analysis.

Fermentation and Proximate Analysis

According to the method described by Izonfuo *et al.* (2005). The samples were fermented in labelled covered containers for 72h. The pH and proximate analysis was carried out at 24 h intervals. Anti-nutritional factors and phytochemical analysis were also carried out

The proximate analysis (moisture content, Ash Content, crude fat, crude protein, crude fiber) of each sample was determined by the method described by Onilude *et al.*, (2005).

RESULTS

From the results obtained in this study, analysis on moisture content showed that plantain peels before and after fermentation recorded 9.90% and 98.07% respectively. For the fat content analysis for both plantain samples, it recorded a reduction from 4.60 to 0.00% respectively after fermentation for 72 hours. Changes were observed in the crude fiber content of fermented plantain samples as shown in Figure 1 which recorded lower values of crude fiber of 0.00 than in the unfermented samples of 12.80%. It was observed that fermentation reduced the protein content of both plantain flour from 7.30 to 0.25% respectively. Figure 1 showed that the fermented sample recorded lower values in total ash content and tannin having 0.23 and 60.50 than the values recorded in unfermented samples of 9.90 and 1662.375% respectively. The change in total titrable acidity of all the samples is also shown in Tables (1 and 2) and Fig. 1. The highest value of titrable acidity was (23.77g/100 lactic acid) as observed within 24 hours for non-degraded plantain samples.

The results of the phytochemicals components of Non-Degraded Plantain peels before and after fermentation are as shown in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1: Nutritional Quality and Phytochemicals Component of Non Degraded Plantain Peels Before fermentation

Parameters	Non Degraded plantain peel (dry sample)
Nitrogen free extract (carbohydrate CHO)	55.93
Glucose %	1.418
Color intensity%	0.348
Color (%Brown)	13.41
Tannin(mg/kg)	1662.375
Terpenoid(mg/kg)	Below Limit of Detection
Phytate(mg/kg)	33.13
Flavonoids(mg/kg)	3194.719
Caffeine(mg/kg)	0.406
Saponin %	0.60
Vitamin A(mg/kg)	1462.01

Vitamin C(mg/kg)	193.618
Titrateable Acidity %	23.77

Table 2: Determination of Nutritional Quality and Phytochemical Component of Non Degraded Plantain Peels after fermentation (3 days)

Parameters	Non Degraded plantain peels (dry sample)
Nitrogen free extract (carbohydrate CHO)	0.99
Glucose	20.60
Color intensity	0.078
-Color (%Brown)	1.29
Tannin	60.50
Terpenoid	Below Limit of Detection
Phytate	10.92
Flavonoids	25.50
Caffeine	2.18
Saponin	0.00
Vitamin A	0.056
Vitamin C	30.05
Titrateable Acidity	23.00

Fig. 1: Proximate composition (%) of plantain peels flour before and after fermentation at 72hrs

DISCUSSION

The results of this work show that fermentation had effect on some of the proximate composition of the non-degraded plantain peel samples. The fermented plantain samples at Day 3 recorded the highest moisture content than those at Day 0. This increase could be as a result of the metabolic activities of microorganisms present, thereby resulting in the release of some extracellular enzymes into the samples (Oboh & Akindahunsi, 2004). This observation correlates with the works reported by Afoakwa *et al.* (2004) and Eromosele *et al.* (2017) who stated that fermentation process may prove a means of improving product functionality and protein contents. This work also observed a decrease in the total ash content after fermentation of the plantain samples. Ash content is known to be a measure of the amount of minerals present in a food sample, and thus, an increase in its level during microbial fermentation could be as a result of incomplete utilization of minerals by fermenting organisms during their metabolism. This result was also found to be similar to that reported earlier (Eromosele *et al.*, 2017).

There was however a decrease in the crude fiber content after fermentation. This does not correlate with the work reported by Eromosele *et al.* (2017) that observed an increase. Fiber containing food are known to expand the inside walls of the colon, easing the passage of waste, thus making it an effective anti-constipation. Furthermore, it lowers cholesterol level in the blood and reduces the risk of various cancers as reported by (Bello *et al.*, 2008). There were also observed decrease in the amount of crude protein and crude fat of the fermented non-degraded plantain samples. These observations therefore favor the utilization of non-fermented plantain flour in the production of healthy local beverages.

There were also changes in anti-nutrient composition of unfermented and fermented non-degraded plantain samples. These anti-nutrients affect the nutritional value of food products and they include flavonoids, alkaloids, glycosides and tannin. The compositions of these anti-nutrients content were found to be higher in all samples before fermentation, and greatly reduced after fermentation. These decreases were attributed to the hydrolysis process during fermentation and are found to correlate with those reported (Eromosele *et al.*, 2017). Tannins are known to bind to enzymes of the digestive tract, affecting

the utilization of proteins and iron absorption with high tannin food. They also reduce the availability of proteins, carbohydrates and minerals through the fermentation of indigestible complexes, breakdown of such complexes will invariably improve the availability of the nutrients. Thus, from the results gotten from this study, it can be said that these anti- nutrients were not completely broken down as the availability of crude protein after fermentation was considerably reduced. There was an observed decrease in total titratable acidity at the end of 72 hours of fermenting the plantain peel samples. This finding is not in accordance with the findings of (Mbate *et al.*, 2008) who reported that pH drops while total titratable acidity increases as the fermentation progressed. This decrease in total titratable acidity could be as a result of the non- dominance of the environment by lactic acid bacteria (LAB) which degrades carbohydrate resulting in acidification.

Previous studies by Ofuya and Nwanjuiba (1990) also revealed that the controlled degradation of substrates by fungal enzymes is dependent on some factors which include incubation time, temperature and pH. Akinyele and Agboro (2007) stated that under favourable environmental conditions, these fungal enzymes degrade the non- starch polysaccharides (NSPs) in the substrates to soluble sugar. However, the sugar content decreases after 7 days due to an increase in the fungal biomass which leads to the depletion of the NSPs hence a decrease in sugar production from the substrates.

CONCLUSION

This research work shows that flour derived from non-degraded plantain peels has high moisture content, low crude protein, no crude fiber, no caffeine and it has high Vitamin C with little cyanide. These proximate factors have proven that it is possible to produce a suitable local drink low in sugar content using non- degraded plantain peels. Plantain flour made using non-degraded plantain peels by the use of oven has been part of the appropriate method for processing of plantain flour. The following are therefore recommended: Production of a local beverage through fermentation of the milled non-degraded plantain peels (flour) which is the most appropriate method of producing a suitable dietary drink. The consistent use of waste plantain peels for production of local beverage in order to reduce the causes of pollution in

the environment. Proximate analysis, nutritional and phytochemical factors should be determined before and after fermentation, that is, analysis should be done on the dry flour sample and the wet fermented flour sample. This research work has described the potentials, nutritional and phytochemical components of non-degraded plantain peels for use on the formulation of local beverages low in sugar content which is suitable for a patient suffering from diabetes.

REFERENCES

- AACC. (2000). American Association of Cereal Chemists. Approved methods of the AACC (10th ed.). St. Paul, MN: The Associations.
- Afoakwa, E. O, Sefa-Dedeh S, Kluitse, Y., Sakyi-Dawson, E. O. (2004). The influence of fermentation and cowpea fortification on quality characteristics of maize based weaning foods. *Paper presented at the second international workshop on food based approaches for healthy nutrition in West Africa: The Role of Food Technologists and Nutritionist, Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso.* 23-28
- Agronomic evaluation of plantain and other triploid Musa. In K. Craenen, R. Ortiz, E.B. Karamura, and D.R. Vuylsteke (eds.). Proceeding of First International Conference of Banana and Plantain in Africa, Kampala, Uganda, 12-18 October, 1996. *International Society for Horticulture*, 540: 125-135.
- Akinyele, B. J. and Agboro, O. (2007). Increasing the Nutritional Value of Plantain Wastes by the Activities of Fungi Using the Solid State Fermentation Technique. *Research Journal of Microbiology* 2(2): 117-124.
- AOAC. (2007). Official Methods of Analysis. 15th Edn., Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington, DC.,USA.,pp:69-88.
- Bains, W. (2001). *Biotechnology: From A to Z*. 2nd Edn. Oxford Press, New York, pp: 384-385.
- Baiyeri, K. P., Aba, S.C., Otitoju, G.T. and Mbah, O. B. (2011). The effects of ripening and cooking methods on mineral and proximate composition of plantain (Musa sp. AAB cv. 'Agbagba') fruit pulp. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 10(36):6979-6984.
- Bello, M. O., Farade, O. S., Adewusi, S. R. and Olawore, N. O. (2008). Studies of some lesser known Nigerian fruits. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 7(1):3972-3979.
- Devos, P., Wilson, G. F. and De Langhe, E. (1978). Plantain resources and potentials in Africa. Paper presented to the AAASA/IITA working on crop Genetic Resources in Africa held at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan.
- Eromosele, O., Ojokoh, A., Adewale, E., Linda, E. and Anyiam C. (2017) Effect of Fermentation on the Proximate Composition of Ripe and Unripe Plantain Flour. *Journal of Advances in Microbiology* 2(3): 1-10, 2017.
- Ighodaro, O. M. (2013). Evaluation study on Nigerian species of *Musa paradisiaca* peels: Phytochemical screening, proximate analysis, mineral composition and antimicrobial activities. *Researcher* 4(8): 17-20.

- IITA (1998). Plantain and Banana Improvement Program-Annual Report for 1997. International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Onne, Nigeria. pp 34-40.
- Izonfuo, W. A. L. and Omuaru, V. O. T. (1988). Effect of Ripening on the Chemical Composition of Plantain Peels and Pulps (*Musa paradisiaca*). *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 45: 333-336.
- Marriott, J. and Lancaster, P. A. (1983). Bananas and Plantains, In: Chan, H.T. (ed.). Handbook of Tropical Foods. Marcel Dekker. New York. USA. pp. 85-143.
- Mbate C., Narvhus J., Treimo J., and Langsrud T. (2008). Isolation, characterization and identification of lactic acid bacteria from bush era: A Ugandan traditional fermented beverages. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*. 80:255-259.
- Nelson, S. C., Ploetz, R. C. and Kepler, A. K. (2006). *Musa* species (bananas and plantains) version 2. In Elvitch, C.R (ed). Species profiles for pacific island agroforestry, permanent agricultural resources (PAR), Holualoa, Hawaii. pp 67-80.
- Odenigbo, M. A., Asumugha, V. U., Ubbor, S., Nwauzor, C., Otuonye, A.C., Offia-Olua, B. I. (2013). Proximate composition and consumption pattern of plantain and cooking banana. *British Journal of Applied Science and Technology* 3(4): 1035-1043.
- Ofuya, C. O. and Nwanjuiba, C. J. (1990). Microbial degradation and utilization of cassava peel. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 6: 144-148.
- Ogazi, P. O. (1996). Plantain: production, processing and utilization. Paman Associates Ltd. Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria. p 305.
- Ogazi P. O. (2013). Pasting characteristics of starch from new varieties of sweet potato. *Tropical Science*, 40: 25- 28.
- Okareh, O. T., Adeolu, A. T. and Adepoju, O. T. (2015). Proximate and mineral composition of plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) wastes flour; a potential nutrients source in the formulation of animal feeds. *African Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 6(2):53-57.
- Oladiji (2009). Gelatinisation of starch and wheat flour starch; A Review. *Food Chemistry*, 3, 293-317. Human Nutrition (Biochemical Integration), Ilepeju Publishers Ltd., Benin City, Nigeria, p300.
- Oladiji, A. T., Idoko, A. S., Abodunrin, T. P., and Yakubu, M. T. (2010). Studies on the physicochemical properties and fatty acid composition of the oil from ripe plantain peel (*Musa paradisiaca*). *African Scientist* 11(1) 73-78.
- Omole, O., Falade, A. and Ayojesutomi, O. O. (2008). Effects of Maturity and Drying Method on the Physico-chemical and Reconstitution Properties of Plantain Flour.
- Osma, J. F., Herrera, J. L. T. and Couto, S. (2007). Application to synthetic dye decolouration. *Dye pigments* 5:32-37.
- Phillip, B., Shittu, A. M, Aiyelaagbe, I. O. O and Adedokun, T. (2009). Economic potentials of plantain and fluted pumpkin intercropping as a poverty reduction strategy in South-western Nigeria. *World Journal of Agricultural Science*, 5(5):525-534.
- Philips, T. A. (1982). An Agricultural Notebook. Longman, Nigeria. p.125
- Scot, C., Randy, C. P. and Angela, K. K. (2006). *Musa* species (banana and plantain), Musaceae (banana family). Species profiles for pacific island agroforestry.
- Shide, E. G., Wuyep, P. A. and Nok, A. J. (2004). Studies on the degradation of wood sawdust by *Lentinus squarrosulus*. (mont). Singer. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 3: 395 – 398.

- Shide, C (2004). Effect of Ripening on the Chemical Composition of Plantain Peels and Pulp (Musa paradisiaca). *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture* 45: 333-336.
- Shodehinde, S. A. and Oboh, G. (2013). Antioxidant properties of aqueous extract of unripe *Musa paradisiaca* on sodium nitroprusside induced lipid peroxidation in rat pancreas in vitro. *Asian Pacific Journal Trop Biomed.* 3(6): 449-457.
- Singh, R., Kumar, M., Mittal, A. and Mehta, P. K. (2016). Microbial enzymes: Industrial progress in 21st century. *Biotechnology* 6(2): 174.
- Stover and Simmonds (2006). Nutrient enrichment of cassava peels using a mixed culture of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Lactobacillus* sp. Solid media fermentation techniques. *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*, 9:46-49.
- Swennen, R. (1990). 'Limits of morphotaxonomy: names and synonyms of plantain in Africa and elsewhere.' In: Jarret, pp. 172-210.
- Fagbemi, T. N. (1999). Effect of Blanching and Ripening on Functional Properties of Plantain (Musa aab) Flour. *Foods Human Nutrition*, 54: 261- 269.
- Wikipedia.org [homepage on the internet] Peel (fruit). Available from: /http://en.wiki/peel-fruit 2009; 1-7
- Zakpa, H. D., Al-Hassan, A. and Adubofour, J. (2010). An investigation into the feasibility of production and characterization of starch from “Apantu” plantain (giant horn) grown in Ghana. *African Journal of Food Science*, 4(9):571-577.